

CARBON FIBER AND WHISKER REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOYS
BY A SQUEEZE CASTING PROCESS

Sin-ichi Towata, Hajime Ikuno and Sen-ichi Yamada
Toyota Central Research & Development Laboratories, Inc.
Nagakute, Aichi, 480-11, Japan

ABSTRACT

Conventional fiber composites and new types of hybrid composites, in which whiskers were distributed among the fibers, were prepared by a squeeze casting process. The mechanical properties and interface chemistry were investigated.

The volume fraction of carbon fibers could be controlled with sufficiently uniform distribution of fibers in the composites by the addition of whiskers. The longitudinal flexural strength changed in proportion to the volume fraction of carbon fibers. The transverse strength was substantially improved by the hybrid technique. The acoustic emission during the flexural tests decreased by the addition of the small amount of whiskers and by the alloying of magnesium.

On the fracture surfaces, the aluminum oxide and aluminum-magnesium oxide were analysed in the pure aluminum matrix composite and the Al-5%Mg matrix composite, respectively. Many platelets of aluminum carbide and the thin interfacial layer (about 10 nm thick) surrounding the fibers were observed at the fiber/matrix interface in the pure aluminum matrix composite.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced aluminum alloys are useful to achieve weight reduction of structural materials, because of the high stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratios. Carbon fibers are expected as reinforcement of aluminum alloys. But, carbon fibers are difficult to be wetted by molten aluminum alloys and react with the alloys to form brittle carbide at high temperatures[1]. Ordinarily, surface coating is performed to improve wettability and to inhibit chemical reaction between fiber and matrix[2].

Recently, carbon fiber-reinforced aluminum alloys are successfully fabricated by squeeze casting[3], which is expected to be one candidate fabrication process for mass production of metal matrix composites.

In the present study, conventional fiber composites and new types of composites, in which whiskers are distributed among the fibers, are prepared by a squeeze casting process. The mechanical properties of composites and the chemistry of the fiber/matrix interface were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Carbon fibers subjected in the present study were high modulus type PAN based ones (modulus:3.9GPa, diameter:7-8micron). Whiskers were silicon-carbide ones (length:10-40micron, diameter:0.05-0.2micron). The carbon fibers with the surfaces attached with whiskers were prepared to fabricate the hybrid composites (Figure 1). Pure aluminum (99.99%Al) and Al-5%Mg alloy were used as matrix metals. Conventional fiber composites and fiber/whisker hybrid composites were fabricated by a usual squeeze casting process. The casting conditions are listed in Table 1.

The mechanical properties of the composites were investigated under the three point flexural mode. The details of the test conditions are listed in Table 2. The surfaces of the test specimens were mechanically polished with 800 grits emery paper.

Acoustic emission (AE) measurements were carried out during longitudinal flexural tests using Dunegan/Endevco 3000.

The fiber/matrix interfacial structure and chemistry were investigated by ESCA and TEM. The fracture surfaces produced in high vacuum were subjected to in-situ examinations by ESCA. TEM analysis of the transverse section of composites was carried out by JEM 200CX. The accelerated voltage was 200kV. The specimens were prepared by milling the thin plate (about 100 micron), using argon ion (5kV).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Microstructure

Figure 2 shows the scanning electron micrographs of polished and etched transverse sections of the composites. Matrix metal was fully infiltrated into the cavities among fibers in both composites. Fairly uniform distribution of carbon fibers were observed. All the fibers are distributed in contact with adjacent fibers and some exhibited the close-packed configuration in the conventional fiber composite, which are reinforced with only carbon fibers. On the other hand, almost the fibers were separated from their nearest neighbor fibers in the fiber/whisker hybrid composite. Silicon-carbide whiskers were uniformly distributed among the fibers with random orientations. The observation with the scanning electron microscopy showed no evidence of interfacial reaction between matrix and carbon fibers or whiskers.

2. Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties were examined under three point flexural mode. The flexural properties with two different matrix alloys and with two types of composites, conventional fiber composites and fiber/whisker hybrid composites were investigated. The results are indicated in Figure 3. The longitudinal flexural strength was similar in both the matrix composites and increased with the volume fraction of carbon fibers. The conventional fiber composites have been reported to have the tensile strength in good agreement with the value predicted by the simple rule of mixture[3].

Figure 1. Scanning electron micrographs of hybrid fibers.

TABLE 1.
Conditions of a squeeze casting process.

<u>pre-heating of fibers</u>	1033 K x 900s in N ₂ gas
<u>pouring temperature</u>	1033 K
<u>pressing</u>	90 MPa x 60s

TABLE 2.
Conditions of flexural tests.

<u>longitudinal test</u>
specimen size : 8 mm ^w x 1.8 mm ^t x 100 mm ^l
span : 90 mm , crosshead speed : 0.033 mm/s
<u>transverse test</u>
specimen size : 10 mm ^w x 1.8 mm ^t x 18 mm ^l
span : 15 mm , crosshead speed : 0.02 mm/s

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs of cross sections of composites. (a) conventional composite, (b), (c) fiber/whisker hybrid composite

Figure 3. Flexural properties of composites. The numbers in parentheses represent the volume fraction of fibers in the composites.

The transverse flexural strength exhibited a contrastive feature against the longitudinal strength. The strength decreased with the increase of the volume fraction of fibers. In other words, the transverse strength was improved by the hybrid technique. There is an extraordinary difference between longitudinal strength and transverse strength. The transverse strength of the Al-5%Mg matrix composites is larger than the pure aluminum matrix composites. The strength difference between pure aluminum and Al-5%Mg matrices is larger in the hybrid composites than in the conventional fiber composites. It is implied from these data that the volume fraction of carbon fibers can be controlled with uniform distribution of fibers in the fiber/whisker hybrid composites.

3. Fracture Morphology

[Hybrid effect on fracture mode]

Figure 4 shows the longitudinal fracture surfaces. The flexural load was applied to the specimen from upper side with a 10 mm diameter punch. The two types of failure modes, compressive failure and tensile failure, were distinctly observed in the fracture surfaces. The area of compressive failure was much larger in the conventional fiber composite [3], which was above 70 per cent of the fracture surfaces, compared with the hybrid composites, in which the compressive failure area was less than 20 per cent of the fracture surfaces. The hybrid technique mentioned in the present study, by which the direct fiber-to-fiber contacts are avoided and the inter-fiber spacing are increased[4], improves the compressive strength of the composites.

Figure 5 shows the characteristics of acoustic emission during the longitudinal flexural tests with stress-deflection curves. Since the size of specimens is the same for the two types of composites, it was found from the stress-deflection curves that the stiffness is slightly larger in the conventional composite. This feature is attributable to the higher volume fraction of carbon fibers.

The total AE counts increased with the flexural stress and was slightly larger in the conventional composite. It is presumed that the micro-crack opening area per event which may be caused by fiber breakage and delamination is smaller in the hybrid composite.

[Effect of alloying of magnesium]

Figure 6 shows the flexural fracture surfaces of the hybrid composite. The fracture surfaces were jagged. The hybrid composites appeared to have failed in a wholly tensile manner. The fracture surfaces exhibited a much greater degree of fiber pull-out. The longitudinal surfaces of the pulled-out fibers were found to be coated with the matrix metal. In addition, it was noted that the length of the pulled-out fibers was smaller in the Al-5%Mg alloy matrix composite. Therefore, these observations suggest that the interfacial bonding between carbon fiber and matrix is stronger in the Al-5%Mg matrix composite.

Many small dimple patterns were observed in the matrix regions around the failed whiskers.

Figure 7 shows the acoustic emission characteristics during longitudinal flexural tests. At lower stress levels, the stiffness was similar for the two types of composites. However, the stiffness of the Al-5%Mg matrix composite is slightly larger than that of the pure aluminum matrix composite at higher stress levels. The AE data exhibited a remarkable difference. Total AE counts increased with the flexural stress. The total counts are notably smaller in the Al-5%Mg matrix composite over the

Figure 4. Scanning electron micrographs of fracture surfaces of composites (a) conventional composite, (b) fiber/whisker hybrid composite

Figure 5. Acoustic emission characteristics of pure aluminum matrix composite.

Figure 6. Scanning electron micrographs of fracture surfaces of hybrid composites. (a) pure aluminum matrix composite, (b) Al-5%Mg matrix composite.

Figure 7. Acoustic emission characteristics of hybrid composites.

entire stress range examined. These characteristics were also observed in other hybrid composites which have different amounts of whiskers. It is suggested from these AE data and fractographs indicated in Figure 6 that micro-failures, particularly interfacial failures diminish with alloying of magnesium.

4. Fiber/Matrix Interface

ESCA and TEM observations were carried out to investigate the effect of magnesium on the carbon fiber/matrix interface.

The specimens were longitudinally shear-fractured in situ within an ESCA equipment to prevent contamination. Figure 8 shows the ESCA spectra taken from the fracture surfaces. For the pure aluminum matrix composite, the aluminum oxide was found to exist on the interface from additional AES analysis[3]. On the other hand, the aluminum-magnesium oxide was analysed in the fracture surface of the Al-5%Mg matrix composite. The half width of the oxygen peak of the Al-5%Mg matrix composite is larger than that of the pure aluminum matrix composite, suggesting that the oxide state is more complex in the Al-5%Mg matrix composite.

From the intensity ratio of magnesium peak to aluminum peak alone, the aluminum-magnesium oxide observed in the Al-5%Mg matrix composite was not clearly identified to be stoichiometric spinel $MgAl_2O_4$.

Figure 9 shows the transmission electron micrographs of transverse sections of the composites. Fine platelets were detected along the fiber/matrix interface. These were identified as aluminum carbide Al_4C_3 from the electron diffraction patterns. The longitudinal direction of the platelets was predominantly perpendicular to the c-axis of Al_4C_3 crystal structure. These interfacial reaction products were more often observed in pure aluminum matrix composite. The periphery of the carbon fibers of the Al-5%Mg matrix composite was more rugged than the pure aluminum matrix composite.

A very thin interfacial layer, about 10 nm thick, was observed around the fiber surface of the pure aluminum matrix composite. The layer could not be clearly identified, but it is likely aluminum oxide[5]. On the other hand, for the Al-5%Mg matrix composite, the interfacial layer was scarcely observed.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions derived from this investigation are as follows:

1. The volume fraction of carbon fibers could be controlled with sufficiently uniform distribution of fibers in the composite by the addition of whiskers.
2. The longitudinal flexural strength changed in proportion to the volume fraction of carbon fibers, when the hybrid technique was employed.
3. The transverse strength was substantially improved by the hybrid technique.
4. The burst of acoustic emission during the flexural test decreased by the addition of the small amount of whiskers and by the alloying of magnesium.
5. On the fracture surfaces, the aluminum oxide and aluminum-magnesium oxide were analysed in the pure aluminum matrix composite and the Al-5%Mg matrix composite, respectively.

Figure 8 ESCA profiles of fracture surfaces.

Figure 9. Transmission electron micrographs of composites.
 (A),(a) pure aluminum matrix composite.
 (B),(b) Al-5%Mg matrix composite.

6. Fine platelets of aluminum carbide and thin interfacial layer surrounding the fiber were observed at the fiber/matrix interface. These interfacial reaction products were more often observed in the pure aluminum matrix composite.

REFERENCES

1. Baker, A.A., Shipman, C. and Jackson, P.W., The short-term compatibility of carbon fibres with aluminum. *Fibre Sci. and Tech.*, 1972, 5, 213-218.
2. Amateau M.F., Progress in the development of graphite-aluminum composites using liquid infiltration technology. *J. Composite Materials*, 1976, 10, 279.
3. Towata, S. and Yamada, S., Strength and interfacial reaction of high modulus carbon fiber-reinforced aluminum alloys. *Trans. Japan Institute of Metals*, 1985, 26, 563-570.
4. Towata, S. and Yamada, S., Mechanical properties of aluminum alloys reinforced with continuous silicon-carbide fibers and whiskers or particulates. *Trans. Japan Institute of Metals*, 1986, 27, 709-716.
5. Tsai Swe-Den, Schmerling, M. and Marcus, H.L., The interface structure in graphite/aluminum composites. *Ceram. Eng. Sci. Proc.*, v2, n7/8, 1981, 798-808.